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THE IMPACT OF VIDEO GAMING DISORDER ON STUDENT MOTIVATION AND ACADEMIC ATTITUDES: IN THE SCOPE OF PUBG

Abstract: In the era of ever-developing technology, people always strive to find new inventions. In fact, over the past few decades, huge improvements have been made in the field of video gaming. Although these novelties brought entertainment to the lives of millions, their detrimental effects have started to emerge within this timeline. In particular, video gaming industries have become a major role player in this regard. Although their prevalence is notable, the impacts that can have on youth started to be noted by researchers and parents. A growing body of research is now homing in on some of these impacts and more are investigating new emerging ones. This review study explores some of these studies and opens new insights to its readers. The main stance of this review is on the scope of the effect of video gaming on students' motivation and academic attitudes. Additionally, this article offers several interventions – cognitive-behavioral therapy, family, school, and society-involved approaches [1]. In this review paper, we examined studies from different sources, such as Google Scholar and SciSpace. The results are that video

gaming disorder elevates the level of depression among students, potentially hindering their academic performance. Specific twelve studied factors that could enhance and hinder students' academic performance are incorporated. We concluded that video gaming disorder can hinder student's academic performance.

Keywords: Academic attitudes, video gaming disorder, academic performance.

Annotatsiya: Rivojlanayotgan texnologiya davrida odamlar doimo yangi ixtirolar topishga intilishadi. Darhaqiqat, so'nggi bir necha o'n yilliklar davomida video o'yinlar sohasida katta yaxshilanishlar amalga oshirildi. Ushbu yangiliklar millionlab odamlarning hayotiga o'yin-kulgi olib kelgan bo'lsa-da, ularning zararli ta'siri bu vaqt oralig'ida paydo bo'la boshladi. Xususan, video o'yin sanoati bu borada katta rol o'ynagan. Ularning tarqalishi sezilarli bo'lsa-da, yoshlarga ta'sir qilishi mumkin bo'lgan ta'sir tadqiqotchilar va ota-onalar tomonidan qayd etila boshlandi. Hozirgi kunda o'sib borayotgan tadqiqot guruhi ushbu ta'sirlarning ba'zilarini o'rganmoqda va yana ko'plari yangi paydo bo'lganlarini o'rganmoqda. Ushbu sharh tadqiqoti ushbu tadqiqotlarning ba'zilarini o'rganadi va o'quvchilariga yangi tushunchalarni ochadi. Ushbu sharhning asosiy pozitsiyasi video o'yinlarning talabalarning motivatsiyasi va akademik munosabatlariga ta'siri ko'lami. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqola bir nechta tadbirlarni taklif qiladi - kognitiv-xulq-atvor terapiyasi, oila, maktab va jamiyat bilan bog'liq yondashuvlar [1]. Ushbu sharhda biz Google Scholar va SciSpace kabi turli manbalardan olingan tadqiqotlarni ko'rib chiqdik. Natijalar shuni ko'rsatadiki, video o'yinlar buzilishi talabalar o'rtasida ruhiy tushkunlik darajasini oshiradi va ularning akademik faoliyatiga to'sqinlik qiladi. Talabalarning akademik samaradorligini oshirishi va to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin bo'lgan o'n ikkita o'rganilgan aniq omillar kiritilgan. Biz video o'yinlarning buzilishi talabaning akademik samaradorligiga to'sqinlik qilishi mumkin degan xulosaga keldik.

Kalit so'zlar: Akademik munosabat, video o'yin buzilishi, akademik ishlash.

Аннотация: В эпоху постоянно развивающихся технологий люди всегда стремятся находить новые изобретения. Фактически, за последние несколько десятилетий в области видеоигр были достигнуты огромные улучшения. Хотя эти новинки принесли развлечения в жизни миллионов людей, их пагубные последствия начали проявляться в течение этого времени. В частности, индустрия видеоигр стала важным игроком в этом отношении. Хотя их распространенность заметна, исследователи и родители начали замечать их воздействие на молодежь. Все больше исследований теперь сосредотачиваются на некоторых из этих воздействий, и все больше изучают новые возникающие. В этом обзорном исследовании рассматриваются некоторые из этих исследований и открываются новые идеи для его читателей. Основная позиция этого обзора заключается в масштабе влияния видеоигр на мотивацию и академические установки учащихся. Кроме того, в этой статье предлагается несколько вмешательств — когнитивно-поведенческая терапия, семейные, школьные и общественно-вовлеченные подходы [1]. В этой обзорной статье мы рассмотрели исследования из разных источников, таких как Google Scholar и SciSpace. Результаты показывают, что расстройство, связанное с видеоиграми, повышает уровень депрессии среди студентов, что потенциально затрудняет их успеваемость. Включены двенадцать конкретных изученных факторов, которые могут

улучшить и ухудшить успеваемость студентов. Мы пришли к выводу, что расстройство, связанное с видеоиграми, может ухудшить успеваемость студентов.

Ключевые слова: Академические установки, расстройство, связанное с видеоиграми, успеваемость.

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Introduction

Amidst the prevailing modern technology, most of the time, one loses his/her conscience due to millions of digital apps, videos, content, and so on, which are available on the media. Today, 5.35 billion people, on average, spend 6.5 hours, or 27% of their time on the Internet daily [2]. The reasons for using the Internet are numerous, from researching to studying to scrolling to gaming. Unfortunately, this twenty-seven percent of the day sometimes is wasted when they are allocated unwisely by inexperienced young people. This unoriented decision led to millions of video-game-addicted player teenagers, who are under 18, encompassing around 8.5% of teenagers overall [2]. Eventually, video gaming disorder is classified by the World Health Organization (WHO) to be a mental health disorder in its International Classification of Diseases (11th edition, 2018) [3]. The negative impacts of video games, including PUBG, on young people should not be underappreciated.

Concerns are long-term consequences including chronic pain, inflammation, numbness, weakness in fingers, hands, or limbs, and feeling anger and bitterness due to toxic gaming communities [4].

Among these concerns, young people's academic attitudes are more worth noting. While some video gaming companies claim to foster collaboration among players, a study has established a positive link between game addiction and suicidal ideations [5]. Ultimately, video gaming leaves more questions regarding its advantages and disadvantages. In this review study, we have encompassed studies that showed the negative effects of video gaming on students' academic performance, either directly or indirectly.

Description for PUBG

Player Unknown's Battlegrounds (PUBG) is a 2017 royale battle game developed by PUBG Studios. It can be played solo or by group with people up to one hundred. In the game, at most hundred players parachute to an island where

they have to find weapons for killing enemies while avoiding being killed themselves. The play zone shrinks over, encouraging teams and individuals to meet. At the end, the surviving team or a player is considered to be the winner of the game.

Purpose of the Study

The study aims to synthesize existing literature and bring detailed studies that show the positive association between video gaming and poor academic performance. Also, it tries to point out places where existing empirical knowledge is lacking, hence encouraging new studies to explore more interventions for the future improvements of youth gaming disorder.

Literature Review

Video game addiction, also known as internet gaming addiction, is characterized as an uncontrolled habit that leads to undesirable consequences in personal and social lives, relationships, and school and work [6]. In its International Classification of Diseases, the World Health Organization (WHO) classified video gaming disorder as a mental health disorder.

Academic performance refers to a student's achievement and success in their educational venture. It is contingent upon a student's endeavor and perseverance in studying. It is typically measured by assessing students' academic knowledge, and how they are

academically competent. Several factors are involved in academic performance that could enhance or hinder it.

Factors that could enhance academic performance

A study led by Abou Naaj concluded that attendance numbers are a major factor that could affect the grade point average (GPA). The type of course that the students chose also influenced academic performance, indicating that different courses demand different levels of skills. Additionally, delivery methods also played a role in students' academic performance, highlighting the need for better and more creative strategies to deliver a subject [7]. In another study, self-regulation was one of the factors for improving academic performance, which highlighted the importance of students' self-regulation when it comes to their studies. Eventually, this ability was also a leading factor in how students utilized the given resources and performed in their courses. This study also mentioned the need for a teacher's encouragement to students to use their course resources wisely to enhance academic performance[8]. Several studies noted the link between the engagement level of students and higher levels of academic performance. Students' emotional engagement, including students' effective reactions to their studies, and their sense of belonging, is a key factor in

enhancing their academic performance. Studies indicated that individuals who are more emotionally engaged in their studies tend to be more educationally successful, and have more learning satisfaction. Psychological capital, which consists of hope, self-efficacy, resilience, and optimism, has increased academic performance. Students with more psychological capital tended to achieve better results in their academic endeavors. Intrinsic and extrinsic motivation was another factor for enhancing academic performance in students. The more motivated the student is the more he/she will be academically engaged, and the better his/her educational performance will be [9]. Apart from emotional engagement, another study underscored the imperativeness of good sleep in better academic performance (Lamma S et al. 2014). The study was cross-sectional and consisted of 471 female and 1672 male students, and was conducted in two universities in Ethiopia. The methodology of this study was to select students for the study using a multistage sampling procedure and collect data through a self-administered questionnaire. While sleep quality was assessed using the Pittsburgh Sleep Quality Index, academic performance was based on self-reported cumulative GPA. The results of this study were that the students with better sleep quality scores tend to achieve greater success in their

academic performance [10]. In addition to external factors, eating habits are revealed to influence the universities' students' academic performance. In their study, Reutere et al. (2020) asked 577 university students in an anonymous online survey about their health-related behaviors, and their current GPA. After monitoring weekly food and drink consumption of students, they showed that certain products such as milk, vegetables, green salad, fruit juice, or fresh fruit consumption rate did not change along with self-reported GPA. Although having breakfast is found to have a positive effect on self-reported GPA, consuming fast food products had a negative impact on it. Ultimately, they concluded that while other factors, including sleep habits, may be imperative, healthy eating habits among students positively affect students' academic performance [11]. Additionally, the importance of physical activity is associated with higher academic performance in secondary school students by a study (François Trudeau et al. 2008). In general, factors that could enhance the academic performance of students are the following:

1. The type of course that the students chose
2. Better delivery methods
3. Students' self-regulation
4. Wise utilization of course resources
5. Teachers' encouragement

6. High level of student engagement in their studies
7. Students' emotional engagement
8. High psychological capital
9. High intrinsic and extrinsic motivation
10. Good sleep
11. Healthy eating habits
12. Physical activity

Factors that could hinder academic performance

In a study by Abdul-Razak Fatawu et al. (2022), the factors that could hinder high school students' academic performance in mathematics are investigated. They employed a series of methods to gather, analyze, and present data. By questioning eighty-one students (51 males and 30 females) from two randomly sampled senior high schools in the Kassena-Nankana Municipality, and analyzing the questionnaires with descriptive and inscriptive statistics, they concluded that lack of student motivation and attitudes towards mathematics was one of the factors that caused students to perform poorly in this subject. Furthermore, they identified the teacher-related factors—absenteeism, and an insufficient amount of time spent on mathematics in classes—as significant factors for hindering student performance in the subject. Moreover, students' socioeconomic factors, including lack of resources or parental inability to provide enough resources to study

mathematics, were also highlighted as a barrier to academic success in the subject. Students' lack of attitudes and awareness towards the subject and a lack of willingness to learn mathematics are linked to lower academic performance in mathematics. While this study revealed student absenteeism to be an irrelevant factor (contrary to previous claims), lack of delivering and learning resources in math was identified as a challenging effect on students' performance in math in selected Senior High Schools [12]. In the next study by Brinda Desai Bradaric et al. (2022), factors ranging from mental health to technology accessibility were found to affect students' academic performance. The study investigated factors that could hinder student academic performance in the scope of expansion of the virtual world during COVID-19. It employed the questionnaire method to gather the data. By enrolling students and teaching faculty in the Bachelor of Science programs at Rush University, they managed to conclude the factors that are affecting students' academic performance. Surveying students revealed that mental health and financial challenges are major factors indicating an impact on a student's academic performance, while faculty members agreed that technology accessibility and stability play a role in students' academic performance. What was in general among

students and faculty members, however, was that the shift to an at-home learning environment was a contributor to students' academic performance. This study emphasized the importance of providing accessible and constant technological opportunities to students while addressing mental health issues among them [13]. A lack of Individual engagement and motivation were noted to be the main factors for lower levels of academic performance. More to that point, sluggish cognitive tempo (SCT) and daytime sleep are highlighted to be among the factors that could hinder the academic performance of students (Kirstie O'Hare et al. 2021). The study led by Kirstie O'Hare surveyed 1628 parents/caregivers of their children aged 6-10 years old and several related data such as child behavior, sleep patterns, and academic performance. To analyze the direct and indirect relationship between sleep-related factors (such as sleep-disordered breathing symptoms, sleep duration, and latency), daytime sleepiness, SCT, and academic performance in reading, writing, and math the team employed structural equation modeling. The study focused on the impacts of SCT, daytime sleepiness, and sleep-related issues on the academic performance of those children. The results of this study were that while SCT was directly associated with poor academic performance in all three domains: reading,

writing, and math, daytime sleepiness was linked to poor reading skills, suggesting that it affects certain academic skills of children. The study concluded that SCT and daytime sleep are mediators in the relationship between sleep and children's academic performance [14]. In another study, researchers led by Shabnam Jalilolghadr (2021) attempted to find a positive link between sleep-related patterns, including sleep duration, sleep onset delay, insufficiency, and poor academic performance. This study's methodology was to utilize a cross-sectional design as a descriptive-analytic approach and to survey 653 adolescents as the sample population, of whom 40% were males and 60% were females. To assess sleep problems, the researchers employed the Pediatric Sleep Questionnaire and BEARS questionnaire for all students. After analyzing the data, it was revealed that various sleep parameters such as sleep duration, sleep onset delay, and insufficiency had a significant impact on academic performance, with differences observed between genders. While boys exhibited higher sleep duration, oversleeping rates, and academic performance, girls showed higher rates of onset delay and insufficiency. The researchers concluded that students who fall asleep easily demonstrate better performance compared to students with sleep onset issues, emphasizing the importance of

sleep quality in school success [15]. Finally, a study led by Corina Benjet et al. (2023) utilized an online survey method to gather data from 1741 freshmen university students in their first year and a follow-up survey 1 year later. The results of this study were that along with other factors internet gaming disorder was associated with severe school impairment and poor social life [16]. To sum up, 12 general factors could affect to academic performance of students negatively, and they are the following:

1. Lack of student motivation, attitudes, awareness, and willingness
2. Teacher-related factors such as absenteeism, insufficient time spent on teaching
3. Lack of resources or parental inability to provide enough resources
4. Lack of delivering and learning resources
5. Mental health
6. Financial challenges
7. Lack of technology accessibility and stability
8. A change in the learning environment from classroom to at-home
9. Sluggish cognitive tempo
10. Daytime sleepiness
11. Sleep onset delay, and insufficiency of sleep
12. Internet gaming disorder

Empirical Evidence: Effects of playing video-games on academic performance

There are several established reasons for playing video games, e.g., stress relief, challenge and competition, relaxation, enjoyment, social interaction, and even mentally escaping from the real world (Sherry et al. 2006). While the discourse regarding playing video games' consequences in the scope of academic performance has already arisen in scientific discussions multiple times, some studies considered certain digital games (which are specifically programmed by teachers/programmers to boost student motivation and academic performance) to be an educational tool to foster students' learning interests and motivation (Choi et al. 2013; Jennifer Henderlong Corpus 2009; Van Eck 2006). In contrast, a study by Drummond & Sauer (2020) found that playing video games before school on weekdays is associated with poorer academic performances in adolescents [17]. Although a direct link between playing video games and a lack of academic performance has not been established, the link between depression, which could be caused by extended periods of video gaming, and the lowered attitudes of students toward their academic perception has been built (Khadijatu Muhammad et al. 2018). In the case of surveying 150 university students K. Muhammad et al (2018) concluded that depression is an important risk factor for failing

a subject or having poor academic performance. Also, they considered gender differences in their study. They concluded that female students are more prone to depression than their male counterparts. Additionally, depression symptoms are common in internet gaming disorder (IGD) individuals without a diagnosis of depression (E. G. Ostinelli et al. 2021). Typically, depression in IGD individuals is recognized by several symptoms including, anhedonia, social withdrawal, poor work and school performances, fatigue, and disruption of sleep-wake patterns (Achab et al., 2011; Burke and Pepper, 2002). A study led by Fezile Wagner et al. (2022) also highlighted that higher levels of depression symptoms among first-year university students are associated with a greater likelihood of progression delay (delay in academic progression), potentially contributing to the low throughput rates observed in South African universities. As for the PUBG-related impacts, although addiction to playing PUBG is so prevalent that it is not only limited to male audiences, its detrimental impacts on this group are higher than on their female counterparts, as per a study conducted by Ali Hassan et al. (2023) [18]. By utilizing an Artificial Neural Network (ANN) model, they found that there is a positive link between engaging in PUBG and the likelihood of elevated impact of media on individuals'

perception. In detail, males exhibited a higher level of cultivation effect – that's, the effect of exposure to media on one's perceptions of reality – than females did. In conclusion, notwithstanding that there is no direct link which is linking video gaming disorder with poor academic performance, depression, which is more prevalent among IGD individuals, can be attributed as one of the causes of poorer academic performance.

Depression & video gaming disorder

Depression refers to a depressed mood and loss of pleasure and interest in activities for a long period. It may feature sadness, difficulty in thinking and concentration, a significant increase or decrease in appetite and time spent sleeping. People experiencing depression may have feeling digestion, loneliness, and may experience suicidal thoughts. Depression comes in two ways: short-term and long-term. Several factors may contribute to individuals' depression, including childhood abuse, sexual abuse, parental treatment of siblings, social isolation/rejection, loss of loved ones, unemployment, stress, work pressure, medical diagnosis, catastrophic injuries, childbirth, bullying, natural disasters, leaving in less green spaces, relationship troubles, jealousy, and separation [19]. In this context, we want to pronounce the role of depression on the academic performance of students. While

depression is associated with stress and depressed mood, many studies have established the association between depression and poor academic performance/achievement (Brunborg et al. 2014; Anand, 2007; Gentile, Lynch, Linder & Walsh, 2004). A study emphasized the PUBG's role, in particular, in depression. In the extensive one-group-oriented study, Lin et al. (2019) discovered a link between playing the immersive game PUBG extensively and higher levels of depressive issues and a sense of isolation. Moreover, they hypothesized that prolonged engagement with PUBG makes young people and adults alike more susceptible to mental health issues. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), depression is estimated to occur in 1.1% of adolescents aged 10–14 years and 2.8% of 15–19-year-olds [20]. In one of the more detailed studies by Céline Bonnaire et al. (2019), gender differences are also considered. In the whole study sample, being male, being alexithymic, and having high depression and anxiety scores were factors associated with IGD, while female depression score was associated with IGD. Also, their study was in line with other previous studies pointing to the negative association between negative effects (e.g. anxiety and depression) and IGD, and showing that some players may play to cope with distress more than to succeed (Billieux et al., 2013). Furthermore, their results

were also in line with a previous study on regular gamers, showing that they have higher levels of alexithymia compared to irregular gamers (Gaetan et al., 2016). To sum up, higher depression levels and video gaming disorders are closely correlated. A study led by Leng Dang et al. (2024) explores the relationship between internet gaming disorder and depression among Chinese undergraduate student gamers over three waves. The study involved 1243 Chinese undergraduate student gamers (of whom 57% were female), and continued for the three-wave duration (wave 1 (W1) at baseline, Wave 2 (W2) at 6 months, and Wave 3 (W3) at 12 months); it also incorporated statistical analysis, including path modeling, to explore the relationships between depression, internet gaming disorder tendency, and metacognitions about online gaming (MOG). Finally, it indicated that depression predicted internet gaming disorder, but not the other way around, indicating a single-directional relationship between the two, while negative MOG, but not positive, predicted both depression and internet gaming disorder [21]. Notwithstanding that it is contradictory to some previous studies (Lemona et al., 2011) [22], a study led by Brunborg et al. (2014) has failed to find a relationship between time spent playing video games and negative outcomes. Nonetheless, this study approved the link

between video game addiction and depression, lower academic, as well as conduct problems. In this study, two wave panel data were used from two surveys of 1,928 Norwegian adolescents aged 13 to 17 years. The surveys included six measurements: video game use, video game addiction, depression, heavy episodic drinking, academic achievement, and conduct problems. Finally, the analysis of the data has been done using first-differencing, a regression method that is unbiased by time-invariant individual factors. The results were video game addiction was associated with depression, and lower academic, and conduct problems, while time spent on video gaming was not regarded as a cause of any studied negative issues [23].

Interventions

Considering all of the negative impacts that video gaming could have on young people, it is imperative to have interventions against those impacts. They vary from cognitive behavioral therapy to medication-involved approaches. Some of the interventions were provided by a study, which was conducted by Yuanyu Yue et al. (2024): balanced gaming habits, implementing time restrictions, reducing screen time among students, and having sound rehabilitation programs. This study utilized the existing literature to highlight video gaming disorder as a mental health disorder. It proposed

multifaceted interventions from which parents/caregivers could start; they included family-involved, school-involved, and society-involved interventions. Family-involved interventions – cultivating balanced gaming habits and implementing time restrictions – are proposed to be significant when it comes to alleviating video-gaming harm to youth. Schools are suggested to implement a wide variety of extracurricular activities to reduce screen time among students. At the societal level, fostering a psychological support system and implementing comprehensive rehabilitation programs are suggested to be imperative to tackle the far-reaching consequences of electronic game addiction.

Methodology

When researching studies we used resources from different institutions and journals. Our review study specifically encompassed studies, that were conducted in 2004 and onwards, that showed the link between video gaming disorder and students' academic attitudes, either directly or indirectly. Most studies we examined were cross-sectional and involved both male and female participants. We mainly used two sources for searching findings: Google Scholar and Scispace.

Results

Video gaming disorder and addiction are associated with poor academic performance and

student well-being. Depression is linked to video gaming disorder and vice versa. Moreover, depression is a main factor in students' failing in their academic endeavors and having poor academic performance. The amount of time spent on video gaming is associated with negative effects. However, other studies' findings suggest that video games' addictive nature, rather than the amount of time that is spent on video gaming, can lead to depression, poorer academic performance, and more conduct problems.

Discussion

We noted that there is an established link between video gaming disorder and poor academic performance among studied individuals. Depression, which is a cause of poorer academic performance, and is more prevalent among video gamers, could be another indirect indicator to conclude that there is an association between video gaming disorder and poor academic performance. This highlights the urgent need for future studies to explore more links between video gaming disorder and academic performance with non-biased individuals. Specific implications of these studies for educators and parents are related to encouraging their students/children to adopt healthy gaming habits.

Limitations

Limitations within the studies we have provided

vary from the smallness of groups of participants to maybe biased responses. Most studies' research scope is limited to certain participant groups and countries. Randomly assigned small groups of studies that might produce bias-based answers are also incorporated, underlining the need for a bigger number of study participants to eliminate bias from studies. Additionally, some studies only focused on specific negative effects, e.g. depression, of video gaming disorder, indicating a potential gap in understanding the full range of video gaming disorders.

Conclusion

By relying on the studies we provided, we conclude that video gaming disorder and addiction can be one of the leading factors that could hinder academic performance, in part because it causes players to get more depressed than non-players. We recommend that parents/caregivers encourage their children to make use of their time efficiently. Teachers should always eir students to allocate their time wisely. Schools should offer more beneficial extracurricular activities for students to cover their time for useful doings. At the societal level, there is a need for sound rehabilitation methods and psychological support systems for those who are struggling with video game disorder.

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